

Redefining doctoral studies: Open Ph.D. as a path to greater opportunities

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Abstract:	Statistics and online discussions highlight significant challenges with traditional doctoral studies. These include difficulties in finding a supervisor, rigid study plans, communicating with supervisors, financial constraints, and burnout among Ph.D. students. This essay proposes the creation of open doctorate programs as a solution to these issues, drawing inspiration from how openness has successfully improved software development (e.g., Linux) and information sharing (e.g., Wikipedia) in the past.
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I. Introduction: Challenges in pursuing a Ph.D.

Pursuing a doctorate today comes with a unique set of challenges. These include difficulties in finding a suitable supervisor, lack of interest from potential supervisors, inadequate treatment of doctoral students, insufficient funding for research and study, and, perhaps most notably, burnout—a problem often exacerbated by these factors.

While individual countries tackle these challenges in their ways, the concept of open doctorates or open Ph.D. programs could provide a universal solution, making doctoral studies more accessible and equitable. The open doctorate model discussed in this essay focuses on removing barriers by granting students greater freedom of choice. However, it is distinct from classical doctorate programs and does not mimic them.

II. Description

2.1. What is a postgraduate program about?

A postgraduate program, particularly a Ph.D., is primarily about learning to conduct research. While Ph.D. students may still attend courses and acquire new theoretical knowledge, the central focus is on learning by doing—immersing themselves in research projects and contributing original insights to their field of study.

In Europe, Ph.D. programs are often designed with the expectation that graduates will continue in academia or research careers. Beyond research, Ph.D. students are frequently tasked with teaching responsibilities, such as assisting with classes. However, these teaching roles are rarely structured to help Ph.D. students develop pedagogical skills.

2.2. What does "open" mean here?

The concept of "openness" as we understand it today began gaining prominence in the 1970s and 1980s. During this time, programmers faced a significant limitation: when software failed to work as expected, they were unable to access its inner workings to fix it themselves. This frustration gave birth to the idea of open source, or what we often refer to as open-(source) software.

One of the earliest and most influential examples of open-source software is the Linux operating system. Linux not only became a free operating system but also one whose underlying code was accessible to anyone. Developers could download it, study it, suggest improvements, and even create their own versions, without restriction. This democratized approach to software development paved the way for openness in other fields.

Decades later, in 2001, another milestone in openness emerged: Wikipedia. As an "open encyclopedia," Wikipedia revolutionized how we access and share information. While its most visible feature is that it is free, the true power of its openness lies in its ability to break down

barriers to knowledge. Wikipedia is available globally through the internet, offering quick access to information in many languages. For example:

- In wealthier regions like the U.S., where the primary obstacle might be the cost of information (tied to expensive higher education), Wikipedia addressed this by providing free access.
- In regions like Africa, where language barriers may prevent people from accessing knowledge in English, Wikipedia introduced localized versions to ensure inclusivity. In areas without internet connectivity, laptops with pre-downloaded content were distributed, further breaking down barriers of learning.

Building on this ethos, Wikiversity was launched in 2006. Wikiversity applies openness to education and research. In the U.S., its main goal is to make education accessible to those who cannot afford traditional institutions. Meanwhile, in Europe, the platform addresses a different need: the demand for flexible, personalized learning experiences. Not every student thrives under a rigid, teacher-driven system, and Wikiversity provides an alternative, allowing learners to study in a way that suits their individual needs. This adaptability has made it popular even in smaller linguistic communities, such as the Czech-speaking population.

These examples illustrate a crucial point: openness does not simply mean "free of charge." Instead, it is about removing barriers—financial, linguistic, or structural—that prevent people from accessing resources. Openness strives to make tools, information, and opportunities available to as many people as possible, regardless of their background or circumstances.

III. Open Ph.D. to address postgraduate problems

3.1. The supervisor silemma

One of the most common challenges faced by today's Ph.D. students is their relationship with supervisors. Issues range from an inability to find a supervisor and initiate their Ph.D. studies, to supervisors who neglect their responsibilities or fail to communicate effectively. This dependency on a single mentor often leaves students feeling unsupported and discouraged.

This raises an important question: Do Ph.D. students need supervisors at all? In the digital age, with abundant resources and testimonials from fellow researchers available online, the traditional supervisor-student model may no longer be the only viable approach. Instead of mandating supervision, why not empower young researchers with access to online courses in research methodologies and let them seek out experts in specific areas which they need?

Furthermore, the current system often fails to ensure quality. If supervisors are inattentive or have conflicts with their students, how can we expect excellent research outcomes? The success of Wikipedia serves as an inspiring parallel. Despite being a platform created by a diverse and relatively inexperienced crowd, it has demonstrated high accuracy—just 10% more errors than Britannica, according to a 2005 study by *Nature*. This suggests that decentralized, open

collaboration can produce results comparable to traditional hierarchical systems. By removing the barrier of requiring a supervisor, open Ph.D. programs could foster greater autonomy and innovation among young scientists.

Today, knowledge is no longer the sole domain of older, higher-ranking academics. With the internet and AI technologies, younger students often excel in information retrieval, linguistic abilities, and technological fluency. If an open Ph.D. model prioritizes self-motivation and resourcefulness, it could outperform the current rigid system in nurturing exceptional researchers.

Finally, the problem of access to specific fields also ties back to supervisors. Many students cannot pursue a Ph.D. in their desired area because no supervisor is available or willing to take them on. An open Ph.D. framework would eliminate this gatekeeping, allowing researchers to pursue their interests independently.

3.2. Flexibility over strict study plans

In many traditional Ph.D. programs, students must create a rigid study plan spanning three to four years. While this requirement teaches strategic planning—an essential skill for grant-based research—it can stifle flexibility. Adapting to a rapidly changing world or shifting research interests becomes difficult, and deviations from the plan may even result in the loss of scholarship.

In an open Ph.D., students could enjoy greater flexibility, designing their own timelines and adjusting their research goals as needed. Strategic planning could be taught as a standalone course, separate from the research process itself, enabling students to learn this skill without compromising their academic freedom.

3.3. The challenge of research equipment and funding

A major obstacle for many Ph.D. students is the lack of access to adequate research tools and financial support. Some departments struggle to provide the necessary equipment, which can hinder the progress of even the most promising researchers.

An open Ph.D. model could encourage collaboration and resource sharing across institutions. Laboratories, particularly those at publicly funded universities in Europe, could open their facilities to external researchers and students from underprivileged universities. This aligns with the European Commission's vision for open science, which aims to remove barriers to research and education.

By sharing resources and promoting equal access, an open Ph.D. system could address disparities in research opportunities while fostering a more collaborative academic environment.

3.4. Burnout and its underlying causes

Burnout is another pervasive issue among Ph.D. students, with many either abandoning their programs or prolonging their studies. However, burnout is often a symptom of deeper problems:

- Poor relationships with supervisors.
- Insufficient financial support, forcing students to take unrelated jobs.

- A lack of freedom to pursue their research interests.

For example, in countries like the Czech Republic, students often struggle to balance academic commitments with financial survival. Addressing these root causes through an open Ph.D. system—where students have more autonomy and flexibility—could significantly reduce burnout rates.

3.5. Other problems

As previously discussed, individuals face a variety of obstacles when pursuing a Ph.D. through traditional pathways. The challenges highlighted earlier were drawn from online discussions among Ph.D. students. However, to effectively design an open Ph.D. program, it is crucial for relevant stakeholders—such as the European Commission—to conduct a comprehensive audit. This audit would identify the most common and pressing barriers faced by aspiring researchers.

Using the findings, a well-crafted framework for an open Ph.D. system could be developed, tailored to address these challenges. While such a framework might not be universally applicable, the open approach may come with variations of Ph.D. programs suitable for prevalent numbers of aspiring scientists in a certain region.

IV. Earning Ph.D. certificate

Despite the growing emphasis on openness in science, the current academic and societal structures remain largely hierarchical. To progress in their careers and contribute effectively to the scientific community, open Ph.D. students will still need the opportunity to earn a recognized Ph.D. title. This certification provides credibility and ensures that their work is acknowledged on par with traditional academic pathways.

Unlike traditional programs, open Ph.D. students may not need to produce a dissertation thesis tied to a specific institution. Instead, their research output could take the form of published scientific papers in open-access journals, which is often more accessible and impactful in the modern academic landscape. This approach not only aligns with the principles of openness but also allows students to bypass institutional constraints while maintaining high standards of academic contribution.

V. Conclusion: A vision for open Ph.D. programs

Many may argue that implementing an open Ph.D. system is impractical or fraught with challenges. However, history offers examples of transformative ideas once dismissed as impossible. For example, few believed that a crowdsourced Wikipedia, open to contributions without stringent editorial oversight, could succeed. Yet, over time, the community developed mechanisms to manage quality and address vandalism, proving the viability of such a model. Today, countless projects thrive on similar principles of openness and collaboration.

Critics may contend that elements of this proposal are flawed or that classical postgraduate studies are indispensable. While traditional systems have their merits, they often fall short in addressing systemic barriers. If we are committed to creating a society with equal opportunities, fostering innovation, and ensuring research funds, an open Ph.D. framework represents a compelling way forward.

The growing global support for open science highlights the urgency of reform. Initiatives like open-access journals, open data repositories, and collaborative research platforms reflect a recognition that traditional models are no longer sufficient. Leading organizations in the U.S. and EU embracing these changes, signaling a clear need for a more inclusive and effective approach to science.

This proposal is not a complete solution but a starting point. A thorough review of this concept, coupled with the development of detailed models for practical implementation, is essential to realize its potential.